

THE INFLUENCE OF WORLD WAR II ON THE TURKISH LITERATURE

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Abstract

Wars have always caused great consequences on earth and changed the economic, social, cultural and political life of countries in a negative way. The consequences of the First World War, which began at the beginning of the 20th century, and the Second World War, which followed immediately after the first, showed the dominance of the "realism" movement in literature.

In this article I represent the effects of Turkiye actions in the literary field, the views of the opposite ideas and events caused by the war. Thus, I have compared both stylistic and discursive changes of the "realism" movement experienced by the war with the ideological movements of other countries.

Keywords: turkish literature, realism, novel, world war II, effects.

Introduction

The psychological, economical, political and cultural impact of World War II on society and individuals has manifested itself in new literary genres through various literary trends in the field of literature. It is possible to read and analyze the points of view of the intellectuals, the political authorities on the war, and the lifestyles of the novels and stories that describe this period. The impact of Turkey's political events on literature during World War II was presented to the reader based on "real events" by writers who lived through the period. It can be said that the "modernization" policy, which the republican thought tried to create, tested the first impact of state-led cultural projects on the intellectuals.

P.N. Boratov describes this effect as the "Kamalist Cultural Revolution":

"The Kemalist ideology plans a complete integration with the industrialized modern Western civilization. This will be made possible by breaking the connection with a past that resists any kind of social structural change in the current time period. On the other hand, at the core of this ideology is the concept of a renewal movement, setting out on the basis of a new culture [2]."

1. The effects of II World War on the story telling in Turkish literature.

In this article, we have taken the words of Fethi Naji, "The true history of the Republic, you can only read it in novels." The researcher emphasizes that history is a science, but the novel is a genre of literature, the effects of historical events on people, the shortcomings in the inner world of a person, if these inner shortcomings do not exist, the novel will be outside of literature. The poverty caused by the war in the people in the economic fields is included in the story book "Sarniç" written by Sait Faig in 1939 and in a chapter of the story that gave the book its name. The story is told through the eyes of a rich vagabond who understands his past life. In the story "Sarniç", our main character eats bread with a little butter on it during the war. But he is happy to be among the people and still full of the joy of living inside, but his wife goes to see her mother and father one day and never comes back because she doesn't want to live in misery anymore.

Because of this, life begins to seem selfish to the one who understands it [6].

In his story "Chelme", published in "Varlig" magazine in 1940, he explains the horror of the rules of war and people's fear of war. Sait Faig ends the story by saying that towards the end of the story, "those who worked in the mill were thrown on olive-oil dolmas and large breads and cheeses, those who had heart attacks and died, and those who were at least satisfied".

In his 1954 book "Alemdagda var bir yilan", "Riza milion-Er", in the example of Riza Efendi, who came to Istanbul from Anatolia in 1937, explains the psychology of people who dream of becoming rich by selling products such as onions, buckwheat, barley, etc.

In the stories of Faig's book "The Boy in the Tunnel", the time is the years of World War II. Sait Faig often compares the stories of people living with their labor in the conditions created by the war economy.

Oktay Akbal, in his 1944 story "First the bread broke", shapes the events by connecting war and bread. It analyzes the fact that the people who died in the war die without knowing the reason and the reflections of this psychology from the state level, to newspapers, to people's behavior.

"First the loaves were spoiled, then everything else.... Because there was a war on earth. People were dying or being killed without knowing why. The word war has become the most used word all over the world. Newspapers were now read with fear [1].

The story teller, compares the joy and happiness of the school years with the world during the time of war, and compares the words of war and peace between the happy society in the past and the unhappy society of that day, and explains his story to the reader.

In the story "There was a harp in the world" by Orhan Kemal, he connects the prison laws with the war in the world. In the story, the narrator, Necati, Kosti, Bob Niyazi, who stayed in prison, describes the economic and psychological effects of the war in the whole story, and then the writer, who often repeats the words "There is a harp in the world", uses analogies such as "The war in the world, the bare feet of hunger, which reminds us of death in the prison".

In the above-mentioned stories, the impact of the economic side of the war on the daily life of the people living in the city is given in an abbreviated form, while

in the novels, the difficulties experienced by the people living in rural areas and engaged in agriculture due to the impact of the war economy are expressed through realistic descriptions of the characters.

2. The effect of world war II on the novels in turkish literature.

Reshat Enis Aygen's "Smell of Soil" written in 1944 is one of the novels that contains World War II. In the novel, Haji Hasan agha in Çukurova is described as abusing the landless peasants with false dolan. Rashad Enis is considered to be the first novel to be written by taking into account the characteristics of Çukurova, the theme, government-people, worker-employer debates, which continued until 1943, when the first land reform began after World War I [9]. Şukran Kurdakul describes this novel as the pioneer of the novels called "rural novels" in Turkish literature due to its characters, events and the environment it reflects [8].

Reşat Enis's novel "The Wailing Wall" also describes the people in Istanbul before the war and during the war. Rashad Enis, who begins with the words "This novel was a wall in front of which we would cry for our social and moral misery", talks about the black market fraudsters who arose during the war due to economic reasons. This novel conveys to the reader that the merchant class, which began to emerge due to the war economy, used newspapers as a tool to incite the people to war, as in World War I.

Oktay Akbal, in his novel "Garipler Sokağı", describes the life of the people of the back street in Fatih region during the war. The writer wants to return to the old Istanbul because he is not happy in the changing Istanbul. There are big differences between old streets and high-rise buildings. Salih, who is the son of a wealthy family, analyzes the lifestyle of that time by living among the people of this area. In addition, the large buildings built in the middle of "Garipler" street, which caused the collapse of half of the neighborhood, mean the destruction of the worlds of the people living on this street. The ones who drove the people to the edge of the city are the bulldozers of Istanbul. The residents of this neighborhood will come from the village to the city and change in the big city. Every person feels the weight of war on this street.

"Many of the residents of the neighborhood are war veterans... The word war reminds all residents of the neighborhood, men and women alike. Men fought for these lands with weapons in their hands, became veterans. Women patiently waited for men, baked bread from straw and sometimes went hungry. For young people and children, the war was just a novelty, they laughed [1]."

The political crisis caused by World War II had a great impact on the intelligentsia. While the war was going on, the conflicting ideological concepts in literary magazines in Turkey became more acute due to the progress of the world war.

Tarik Bugran's novel "Black Amber", published in 1954, explains the loneliness of the nationalist Turkish intelligentsia due to his inability to express his thoughts in front of dictatorial regimes during World War II, based on the relationship between Fernando and Sofia.

Tarik Bugra also criticizes Italian fascism in this novel [3].

Ahmet Hamdi Tanpınar, in his 1949 novel "Huzur", synthesizes the cultural history of Turkey from the east to the west and conveys the ideas of the intellectual of the republic to the reader. Tanpınar, in his own words, understood the National Struggle, which was born "at the gate of the century", which was the collapse of the empire and the rebirth of the Turk, and then lived through World War II. Reading history books and experiencing the war influenced Tanpınar's novels [5].

"Comfort, in terms of time, begins the night before World War II, and ends on the day the war is declared."

In the novel, topics such as the beauties of Istanbul, music, love, history, and philosophy are discussed separately in four chapters such as "Ihsan, Nuran, Suat, Mumtaz".

The novel progresses through 3 main themes: Ihsan's illness, World War II, Mumtaz and Noura's love.

Tanpınar always talks about wars that changed the rules of society. The writer shows us all the chaos of life, which he views from the background of his rich cultural and life experience, from the spectrum of dreams and dreams, past and future. Khalide Edip Adıvar's novel "Endless Fair" was published in 1946.

It tells the story of the lives of the families of Istanbul, who became rich through the black market by profiteering during World War II, their perspectives on life, their commercial relations, and their attitudes towards the war is a centre of novel.

The novel begins with a young girl named Ayşe, who is studying in high school, entering a story contest in which she tells about her parents and coming first and thanks to her teacher Ali Bey Ayşe proves herself and getting popular the rich circle called "two Thousands". The author sees the real rich of Istanbul as different from the new rich, especially in terms of culture. The Bolluk family, one of the real rich people, is one of the former rich people who are not counted among the two thousand, who care about British culture, not Hitler's Germany, and who are not visible to the public. Ayşe also starts teaching the Bolluks' children. Süleyman Bolluk, on the other hand, enjoys constantly chatting about literature with Ali Bey. The expert makes fun of Safi-Türk's belief in Hitler.

In the novel, the positive characters created by the author are Ali Bey, Ayşe, Safi-Türk's nephew Burhan, and journalist Firuzan Tıngır. Firuzan Tıngır is a society journalist. He writes jokes in Haykır newspaper. Temperamentally, he does not belong to any party circle and tries to take his revenge with very bitter sarcasm on the ground and time that shackled his tongue and pen. The modern world, war, and the economic real world of the two thousandths are presented through Tıngır's eyes, sometimes critically and sometimes sarcastically.

According to İnci Enginün, the journalist type appears in many of Khalide Edib's novels. In the "Endless Fair" and "The Pieces of Life" he wrote later, he emerges as a kind of apostle of truth who scrutinizes society [15].

Another positive character is Safi-Turks' nephew Burhan, who was educated in America. He studied at

university in America and worked in various jobs when his scholarship was terminated. Expert Safi-Türk says, "everything is measured in money." According to his mother, he is an idealist with deep pockets, which is diametrically opposed to his thoughts. Speaking about "culture-art" and "east-west" issues, Burhan states that politics should not interfere in such conversations. He thinks that ideas should be free and that this can only be done with people who have no interest in society.

At the end of the novel, Samet Şaşırtmaç finds himself in danger when his irregularities are revealed [16].

He withdraws from the white and black markets in the trading area, goes crazy. Safi-Türk sells its shares. He wants to join the abundance group.

Honest people engaged in trade; Those who were complacent and had no political backing, compared to the Şaşmaç group, regarded this as a harbinger of cleanliness in the commercial world.

Khalide Edip Adıvar states that the writing of the work "Endless Fair" is similar in terms of a novel, but essentially, war riches appeared in Istanbul, then young people became fond of cinema and dancing, and the situation of the civil servant class was quite sad [16].

Result

The great impact of World War II on the Turkish states is known to everyone. Staying out of the war was a victory for the politicians of the time, including İsmet İnönü, the then president of Turkey. But the impact of the war on people was bound to show itself in the literature of the time. Novels and stories have been a mirror of all spheres of social life, economic or political.

While most of the stories and novels we have reviewed explain the impact of the economic situation created by the war on the people's lifestyle, Halida Edip Adıvar's novel "Sonsuz Panayir" is a critical work that reflects the lives, living, and thoughts of the rich during the war.

As a result, after this period, some writers in the history of Turkish literature called them the "1940 generation" because of their stance against the war and the political and economic views they criticized. Sabahattin Ali's novel "The Devil Within" is analyzed in terms of Turanchi intellectuals, great personalities of the time, and political thoughts as a whole. Although he expressed a biased opinion, Sabahaddin Ali had strong reasons to write such a novel. Rifat Ilgaz compared

Turkey with "Dark Nights" during the Second World War. Ahmet Hamdi Tanpınar, influenced by Albert Sorel's quote "War is a disaster", shows the ups and downs in the inner world of the character he created in the novel "Peace", and analyzes the outside world with his daily life observations. As we have seen, World War II has been the subject of analysis in almost all aspects both in stories and novels.

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